

Representation of Women in the Family Structure in *The Blue Hour*

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Abstract:

The representation of women in family structures is a significant theme, reflects social expectations, gender roles, and the emotional intricacies of women's lives. Paula Hawkins' novel The Blue Hour presents complex female characters whose identities and experiences are shaped by family relationships, personal struggles, and societal pressures. This research paper examines the representation and status of women within the family framework in the novel, focusing particularly on the character of Vanessa Chapman and other female character connected to her life. The study analyses how the novel portrays women's roles, responsibilities, and emotional conflicts within familial and social relationships. Through a close reading of the narrative, the paper explores themes such as isolation, identity, and psychological depth.

The study attempts to understand how Hawkins presented women's experiences and challenges traditional views of women's positions within the family. The novel reveals that women are not merely passive members of the family but with complex emotions, desires, and action. However, the paper argues that The Blue Hour presents a nuanced portrayal of women's lives, demonstrating how family structures influence their identity, choices, and psychological development.

Keywords: *Women Representation, Family Structure, Identity and isolation, Feminist Perspective, Psychological Depth.*

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To study concept of Family
- 2) To examine the representation of women in the family structure
- 3) To study the importance of family relationships in contrast to an isolated life in the novel The Blue Hour
- 4) To study impact of male-dominated on n the representation of women in the family structure society

Research Methodology:

This research employs analytical and interpretative methods to analyses research articles, scholarly papers, and primary literary sources.

Concept of Family:

Family is a social unit in which individuals get safety and fulfil their basic needs, as well as emotional, mental, and psychological support. Family can generally be of two types: joint family and nuclear (separate) family. In every family, members try to maintain healthy relationships by understanding one another's thoughts and emotions and by supporting each other.

According to K. Davis, 'Family is a group of people whose relations to one another are based upon consanguinity and who are therefore kin to one another.' Another definition of family is given by Elliott and Merrill, who state that 'Family is a biological social unit composed of husband, wife, and children.' Thus, according to the traditional concept, family is mainly based on

blood relationships. However, in the modern age, this concept has changed. Many people believe in living relationships, which can create a temporary form of family.

In this research paper, two personalities, Vanessa Chapman and Grace Haswell are discussed. For both characters, the concept of family is different.

Portrayal of Independent Women:

The novel *The Blue Hour* by Paula Hawkins, published in 2024, presents the story of Vanessa Chapman, a well-known artist, painter, and sculptor who lives alone on the isolated Eris Island. Art is her passion, and most of her paintings reflect her emotional and inner psychological condition. Vanessa devotes her life to artistic creation and finds satisfaction and freedom through her art work. However, her devotion to professional art and living independent life, she experiences emotional instability and loneliness. Even though she lives in isolation, she still longs for emotional connection with her husband.

Vanessa expresses her deep attachment to art in her diary when she writes, “I barely notice time, I hardly eat, hardly write. I am consumed; feel I need nothing else. Working with ceramic is joy. None of the anxiety I feel when painting there is such a freedom with clay: nothing is set, nothing decided, nothing finished until it is fired” (Hawkins, 2024, p.100). This statement shows how art becomes a source of fulfilment and personal expression for her.

Julian Chapman, her husband, faces financial difficulties, and Vanessa supports him during that time, which reflects her strength and independence. When she later learns about Julian’s affair, she chooses not to interfere in his life, but not having divorce from him, she did not want to leave her family, that shows her emotional maturity and self-respect. However, she still cares for him deeply. After learning about

the accident of his girlfriend, Vanessa writes in her diary, “Julian wasn’t with her, thank God. Poor, poor Julian. My heart aches for him...” (Hawkins, 2024, p.135). These thoughts reveal that although Vanessa is independent and strong, she also experiences deep emotional attachment and concern.

Another important character in the novel is Grace Haswell, a medical practitioner who lives independently. She does not belong to a conventional family structure based on marriage or blood relations. Instead, her close relationship with Vanessa Chapman represents an alternative form of family based on companionship and emotional support. According to Britannica, family is defined as “a group of persons united by the ties of marriage, blood, or adoption, constituting a single household.” However, in the case of Grace, the concept of family extends beyond traditional definitions. Her independent life and emotional connection with Vanessa show how women in the novel construct their own family structures. Thus, Grace’s character reflects the idea of an independent woman who redefines the meaning of family. Vanessa becomes the most important person in Grace’s life, almost like a family member. They are not related by blood; Grace gives emotional and practical support to Vanessa. She describes her devotion by saying, ‘I was always here for her, from that very first time we met, when she broke her wrist. I was the person she relied on... I cooked for her... I fixed things when they broke... I listened when she talked... I protected her... and I was here to pick up the pieces after everything fell apart.’ (Hawkins 167–168). This statement shows Grace’s deep sense of responsibility and attachment toward Vanessa. Through her actions, Grace appears as a strong and independent woman who offers emotional and psychological support, and fulfilling a role similar to that of a family member in Vanessa’s life.

Isolation and Psychological Identity of Women:

Vanessa Chapman is portrayed as a self-reliant and independent woman in *The Blue Hour* by Paula Hawkins. However, her isolation from family and society creates a deep longing for human connection in her life. Living alone on Eris Island, becomes bored and she feels suffocated in the same place. The freedom she once desired eventually becomes a form of punishment for her. Although she achieves name and fame as an artist, she carries deep grief within herself. Vanessa expresses her loneliness and emotional pain through her diary. She writes, 'This freedom is intoxicating, again she expressed her in diary, I eat when I please, work when I please, come and go when I please. I answer to no one, only the tide' (Hawkins, 2024, p. 20).

Psychological identity can be understood through the psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud, who explains that human personality is of three parts: the Id, Ego, and Superego. The Id represents instinctual desires, the Ego mediates between reality and desires, and the Superego reflects moral values and social norms. The interaction of these three elements individual's psychological identity and behavior (Freud, 1923). In this way psychological identity is the way that person understands their own personality, feelings, and behavior, which forms sense of self.

From a psychological perspective, Vanessa initially appears mentally strong and capable of adjusting to her surroundings. However, repeated accusations and blame from her family members weaken her inner stability. Her sister-in-law blames her for disturbing Julian's life and holds her responsible for his disappearance. Such accusations gradually break Vanessa's psychological identity from within, and reveals emotional impact of isolation and social judgment on women. She wrote letter to one of her friend Francis and writes, 'Could I come and

see you? If only I could just get away from this place for a while, I think I would start to feel myself.' (Hawkins, 2024, p.208)

Grace Haswel is mentally and physically strong and independent she experienced loneliness and learns more thing from life, the entry of Vanessa in her life is one of the happiness for her, she got attached with her and the interference of others in Vanessa's life is unbearable for her, she has always a fear in her mind that Vanessa will leave her and she will be again lonely. She had taken wrong action for this and the isolation made her strong enough to handle any crime. The isolation has positive and negative impact on her.

Grace Haswell's psychological identity in *The Blue Hour* reflects a combination of emotional strength, responsibility, and inner vulnerability. Grace is presented as a practical and independent woman who works as a medical practitioner and lives with Vanessa. Her ability to manage difficult situations show that she is mentally strong, and responsible. She takes care of Vanessa and supports her during emotional instability of Vanessa, which highlights her nurturing and protective nature.

However, Grace also experiences emotional pressure and internal conflict. Her close relationship with Vanessa creates a deep sense of attachment, responsibility, and concern for her well-being. The emotional bond is none than expectation of her from Vanessa, Grace did not tolerate disappearance of Vanessa from her lifetime. These experiences shape her psychological identity as a woman who appears strong outwardly but internally carries emotional sensitivity and concern for others.

Emotional Exploitation of Women in Family Relationships:

The character of Vanessa Chapman represents how women experience emotional exploitation within family relationships even

though she is independent and strong. Although Vanessa is a successful and self-reliant artist, she suffers emotional betrayal from her husband Julian, who engages in an extra-marital relationship. Instead of supporting Vanessa, Julian's sister supports him, which isolates Vanessa emotionally.

During the times of financial crisis, Julian becomes dependent on Vanessa, and she supports him with trust and loyalty as she loves him by accepting him with his drawbacks and mistakes. However, he takes advantage of her generosity by secretly selling some of her paintings for his own benefit and pretends to show care and affection towards her, but his concern appears only when he needs her support. This behaviour reflects the emotional exploitation faced by women in family relationships. Vanessa is treated as an important family member only in times of difficulty, while at other times her emotions get neglected.

Grace Haswell, who does not have a biological family of her own, creates a sense of family through emotional relationships and companionship. For her, family is not limited to blood relations but includes the people with whom she lives, spends time, and shares her thoughts and feelings. She dislikes loneliness and therefore values emotional bonds deeply. When her old friend Nicholas Riley unexpectedly enters her life while he is suffering from a serious illness, Grace accepts him and provides medical treatment and care. His presence gives her a sense of emotional completeness, and she begins to treat him like a member of her family. She looks after him with affection and responsibility, believing that they can build a supportive life together.

Grace even expresses her willingness to take care of their future by assuring him, 'You don't need to work at all, not right away. I'll look after us for a while. We will hang out. Keep each

other company' (Hawkins, 2024, p. 298). This statement reflects her emotional commitment and her desire to create a stable familial bond. However, this emotional investment eventually leads to disappointment when Nicholas's behaviour changes and he expresses the desire to leave and settle elsewhere. Despite Grace's care and sincerity, he fails to reciprocate the same level of emotional attachment.

Thus, it highlights how women's emotional dedication within relationships can sometimes lead to exploitation. Even though she is professionally independent and mentally strong, her emotional vulnerability allows her to be deceived and hurt within a male-dominated society.

Conclusion:

The role of women in the family is mainly to care for and support the family. Earlier women were housewives, but now many women are working and becoming independent and self-reliant. However, society still often sees women as vulnerable. Even today, women are expected to maintain family relationships and emotional balance.

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